

Research Article

Enhancing Summarizing Skills Through 'Mix & Match' Activity

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Abstract: Many students struggle with summarizing during reading lessons due to difficulty identifying main ideas, distinguishing key points from details and organizing information coherently. This project introduces a Mix and Match kit designed to make summarizing practice more interactive, scaffolded and enjoyable. The activity fosters communication, teamwork and critical thinking, offering an interesting alternative to passive reading tasks. Initial classroom use has shown increased student motivation and improved summarizing performance, particularly among ESL learners. The kit is adaptable to various levels, making it suitable for language classrooms. It addresses a real classroom need with a creative solution, offering value to both educators and learners in the effort to improve reading comprehension outcomes.

Keywords: reading comprehension; summarizing; reading skills

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1. INTRODUCTION

Reading comprehension is a fundamental skill in language education, which enables learners to extract and construct meaning from texts. Among the various strategies to master comprehension, summarizing stands out as a critical technique. It aids students in identifying main ideas, distinguishing supporting details and synthesizing information, therefore enhancing their overall understanding. However, many learners encounter difficulties in summarizing texts effectively. These difficulties are often caused by limited vocabulary, inadequate grasp of text structures and a lack of strategic reading approaches.

Recent research highlights the effectiveness of summarizing strategies in improving reading comprehension. For instance, Dergham (2024) demonstrated significant improvements in secondary school students' abilities to simplify texts and extract main ideas following targeted summarization training. Similarly, Ramirez-Avila and Barreiro (2021) found that elementary school students exhibited enhanced comprehension of narrative texts after engaging in summarization activities. Sujarwo et al (2023) also suggests that implementing summarization strategies effectively enhances reading comprehension and student engagement in EFL contexts. However, despite these positive outcomes,

traditional summarization methods may not sufficiently engage learners or cater to diverse learning styles.

The Mix & Match activity kit is designed to meet with the following objectives: to make reading practice fun, interactive and engaging, to help learners improve their summarizing skills by focusing on identifying main ideas and making inferences, and to support learners in developing better understanding of text structure through hands-on tasks.

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

This project is developed to address the gap in providing practical and engaging solutions for summarizing tools that can aid reading comprehension. It is designed to make summarizing practice more interactive, scaffolded and enjoyable, away from traditional worksheet-based approaches. The *'Mix & Match'* kit consists of a durable board, reading passages, sentence strips and key idea cards that students must match, rearrange and summarize collaboratively. These materials are designed to guide learners through the process of analyzing a text, breaking it down into essential parts and matching it to the summarized form. It helps learners build core reading comprehension skills such as identifying main ideas, making inferences and organizing content.

In addition to improving summarizing skills, the activity fosters peer collaboration, communication and active learning. The tactile and visual components also cater to multiple learning styles, making the tool suitable for differentiated instruction. The kit is adaptable for different text genres (narrative, informational, argumentative) and is accompanied by step-by-step instructions and assessment rubrics.

3. FINDINGS

The findings from the students' feedback strongly support the effectiveness of the Mix & Match activity in enhancing reading comprehension, particularly in relation to identifying main ideas and overall understanding of the text.

Figure 1. Students' perception on the Mix & Match activity

Based on Figure 1 above, 79% of the students strongly agreed that the activity helped them understand the main idea of the text, while another 15% agreed. This means that a total of 94% of the respondents had a positive perception of the activity in aiding their understanding of main ideas, which is a key component of summarizing. Only 7% remained neutral, and this shows wide acceptance of the tool's effectiveness. Additionally, 79% of the students also strongly agreed that the activity helped improve their overall reading comprehension skills, with 7% agreeing and 15% remaining neutral. This suggests that while a majority saw direct benefits in comprehension, a small portion may need more exposure to the method or had varied reading levels that affected their perception. Lastly, when asked if the activity was useful for learning in general, 79% strongly agreed, 15% agreed and 7% were neutral. This shows that learners not only found the activity effective but also meaningful and relevant to their learning experience.

4. DISCUSSION

The findings highlight strong support for the effectiveness of the Mix & Match activity kit in enhancing students' ability to summarize texts and improve their overall reading comprehension. The majority of the participants strongly agreed that the activity helped them understand the main idea of the text, which suggests that the activity successfully guided students in identifying and organizing key information from texts, which is a basic component of effective summarizing. Additionally, the activity also improved their comprehension skills and these results suggest that the Mix & Match activity kit provides the structured scaffolding needed to deepen their understanding, especially for learners who may struggle with traditional and passive reading activities. The small percentage of neutral responses could indicate that some learners may require additional practice or have varied reading proficiency levels. Moreover, the consistency in positive responses regarding the usefulness of the activity for learning highlights its potential as a student-friendly and adaptable tool for reading instruction. The interactive, hands-on format likely contributed to its effectiveness by promoting active engagement, critical thinking and peer collaboration. These findings aligned with previous research (Dergham, 2024; Ramirez-Avila & Barreiro, 2021), which emphasizes the value of summarizing as a strategy to improve reading comprehension, especially when delivered through student-centered approaches.

5. CONCLUSION

The data suggests that the Mix & Match activity is highly effective and well-received by students. It supports comprehension and summarizing skills in a way that is both engaging and pedagogically sound. The success of the implementation of the activity may also be attributed to its multi-sensory nature which combines visual aids, movement and verbal discussion that caters to various learning styles and fosters a deeper connection to the texts. It also promotes higher-order thinking skills such as inference, analysis, and synthesis, which is essential for strong academic literacy. In short, the Mix & Match summarizing kit addresses an important instructional gap by changing a complex reading skill into an accessible, enjoyable classroom activity. Its effectiveness, ease of implementation and positive reception among students suggest strong potential for wider classroom adoption and even commercial application in literacy-focused programs.

References

- Dergham, R. A. S. (2024). The Impact of Using Summarizing Strategy on Secondary Student's Reading Comprehension Skills. *Journal of Faculty of Education for Women*, 35(138.3), 1-42. <https://doi.org/10.21608/jfeb.2024.303253.1961>

- Ramirez-Avila, M. R., & Barreiro, J. P. (2021). The Effect of Summarizing Narrative Texts to Improve Reading Comprehension. *Journal of Foreign Language Teaching and Learning*, 6(2), 94–110. <https://doi.org/10.18196/ftl.v6i2.11707>
- Sujarwo, A., Setiyo, B., Suhendi, S., Istiara, F., & Hastomo, T. (2023). Enhancing reading comprehension through the utilization of the summarization strategy. *Journal of English Language Teaching and Applied Linguistics*, 9(2), 131–145. <https://doi.org/10.52657/js.v9i2.2109>